

GLOBALIZATION AND ITS SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL ISSUES

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Abstract. *This article discusses the content of education and training issues, the impact of globalization, ensuring the harmony of universal and national moral values, increasing virtual dependence, the influence of young people by foreign ideas, and their negative consequences held.*

Keywords: *education, youth, alien idea, spiritual crisis and ideological gap, globalization, nature, spirituality.*

The main source of study and elimination of global problems and the factors that cause them by representatives of all sectors of our society is the organization of education and training in accordance with national and universal moral values, the purposeful and effective use of modern pedagogical technologies is recognized as urgent. is doing.

In fact, it is expedient for human society to organize the optimal options for the harmony of spirituality and enlightenment based on democratic principles and relying on ethno-psychological factors as the only way to eliminate these problems.

The analysis of the scientific literature on the analyzed topic shows that in the early stages of the globalization process, they could not imagine the true nature of it, so they believed that globalization is a positive phenomenon that removes obstacles to free trade and unites the entire national economy. However, this process is not as they say, but penetrated into all spheres of the society and had an impact on its national abilities, lifestyle, beliefs and psychology.

Today, globalization benefits developed countries and has mechanisms that lead third world countries, that is, developing countries, in particular, countries with a low economy and insufficient competitiveness in the world arena, towards a crisis. Regarding globalization, its role in the life of the state and society, I.I. Belyaev put forward scientific comments that "...globalization can negatively affect the social and spiritual life of other (developing) countries"[2].

The real reality of the information society requires us all to approach today's changes from the point of view of conscious and rational factors. The relationship between them is extremely complicated, and even, in some cases, they show their conflict.

In fact, it is no secret that one of the problems that concern sociologists, psychologists, spiritualists, pedagogues and humanitarian experts in the study of the impact of integrated development in our society on youth education is the "idea of cosmopolitanism" and "mass culture".

A number of scientific-theoretical suggestions and recommendations have been put forward in order to eliminate these problems, and issues of minimizing the negative impact of these foreign ideas on the life of young people, in particular, on the lifestyle of society, are being put forward. Full implementation of the advanced conceptual mechanisms developed on the basis

of these approaches and of socio-spiritual importance to all aspects of society's life remains the demand of the time.

Multipolarity and ideological pluralism, "global trade networks", "civilizational integration", "mass culture" that emerged in the 90s of the 20th century are a huge, interconnected world that acts on the basis of the unity of dialectical communication and conflicts. requires that it function as a system that has the power to influence.

The laws and principles of the development of this process, according to some experts, the emergence of an economic and cultural space in the whole world, as well as the creation of a single human commonality, the establishment of a single space in the process of information exchange will lead to the emergence of a new form of personal civilization [10]. There are assumptions.

From this point of view, it is necessary not to forget the constant awareness that the cosmopolitical idea and its existence may threaten the future of independent countries with a long historical past, rich national values and a great future, and the prospects of their youth.

Today, it is the demand of our time to thoroughly study issues related to the spirituality and culture, consciousness and thinking of young people from a scientific point of view, to create a socio-psychological "isolating" mechanism that can protect them from external influences. remains.

The idea of the socio-psychological "isolating" mechanism put forward by us serves to ensure the spiritual life of the state and society, its development, as well as the perspective of the youth, while serving to ensure that the ancestors remain a worthy generation, as a nation, its existence for thousands of years. provides.

In conclusion, it is appropriate to implement scientific and pedagogical approaches in this area that are comprehensive, relevant to the life of the state and society, and have socio-political significance based on the motto of New Uzbekistan.

In this:

-it is necessary to direct the educational content to the formation of immunity against information and informational attacks, and to coordinate innovative pedagogical technologies with the existing process (in this case, the culture of using the global information network for learners, developing their consciousness and a healthy worldview, and referring to sources that motivate not to have an emotional approach to any information, to develop the competence of analyzing and synthesizing existing information, not to get acquainted with sources that cause mental stress that are strange and incomprehensible to them, that have a negative effect on their psyche, to promote and promote them not to, which involves communicating openly, objectively, comprehensively in a language they understand, using paralinguistic factors regarding their future and prospects);

- in order to achieve quality and efficiency in all stages of the educational system (from preschool to higher education), it is necessary to introduce the concept of "educational diet" into the pedagogical process it is necessary to take into account their age and psychological state, interests, abilities and talents. Also, the resources transmitted by the pedagogue should not cause strong mental stress to the learner, should not form an antipathy towards reading and research, and mastering, on the contrary, quickly and it is necessary to reflect approaches that incorporate a combination of motivational factors to easy learning, to increase the desire to learn, to establish a sympathetic attitude towards education);

- to prevent existing and growing virtual dependence and to inculcate socio-psychological mechanisms of preserving "technogenic culture" within the "influence" of national and universal spirituality into the life of society on the basis of modern pedagogical factors (most members of society are active on social networks lib, they are becoming more and more alienated from their relatives and family members, growing indifference to each other as a result of the growing coldness in their character in relation to talking with their children and other family members, fatherhood and motherhood, filial duty and Obligations are neglected, the content of education and training is seriously affected, it creates a moral vacuum, this vacuum is filled with other foreign factors, as a result of which family conflict increases, national and universal values, and the stability of society are invisible. increasing threat, interpersonal relations to create the possibility of bringing all types of conflicts to an unmanageable level with the popularization of hidden and open forms).

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